

TENSILE STRENGTH PREDICTION OF BOLTED REPAIR ON COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

The method of predicting the tensile failure strength of bolted repair of composite laminates was studied. Aiming at predicting the typical net-tension failure of bolted composite repair, the Finite Fracture Mechanics model was employed combined with a two-stage analysis method. The bolt load distribution was first calculated using the global analysis method. After obtaining the fastener load from the first-stage global analysis, detailed stress and stress intensity factor analyses were conducted around individual fasteners and the cutout. The stress distributions and stress intensity factors around the holes were then used to evaluate the net-tension failure strength of the composite panels. The proposed model was applied to predict the failure strength of three bolted repaired composite laminates with circular, elliptical and oblong cutouts. Results showed that the failure mode, failure location and the failure strengths predicted by the proposed model were consistent with experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Among the major advantages of laminated composite structures over conventional metal structures are their comparatively high strength to weight and stiffness to weight ratios. Aeronautics which are sensitive to the weight, might be the best applications for composites. Since the laminated composites are vulnerable to the impact, the unexpected damage caused by an accidental impact occurs very often. Thus, composite repair becomes an important technology to reinforce the strength of the damaged composites.

The methods of composite repair include adhesively bonded repair and bolted repair. Much of the analytical work in the literature relating to composite repair has focused on the bonded repair, while less attention has been paid to the bolted repair. The technique of bolted repair is relatively simple in comparison with bonded repair which require perishable patching compounds, complex patching equipment and careful surface preparation. Thus, the bolted repair may be a better choice when the fast repair is required or in the field repair where less equipment is available.

An important part of the repair process is the prediction of the strength of the bolted repair area. Thus, an assessment of fastener loads and stress status in bolted repairs is essential. Many methods have been proposed in the literature to determine the fastener loads and the stress status in bolted repairs, including stiffness method^[1,2], the finite element method^[3-7], complex potential-variational method^[8-9] and the boundary element^[10].

Among the previous investigations, Her and Shie^[1] analyzed the bolted repair of composite laminates based on the assumptions of rigid bolts and compatible deformation between laminate and patch. The loads transmitted to the external patches through the bolts are determined. This method take into account the effect of the damage hole on the flexibility of the plate. However, the effect of bolt flexibility is neglected. Xie^[2] presented an improved spring-mass method to determine the load transfer in composite bolted repair. Both the effect of open-hole damage on the stiffness of the composite panel and the effect of bolt flexibility were accounted. For multi-column bolted repair, the

total stiffness of the bolts in a row was computed based on the principle of superposition. The obtained skin stiffness and bolt stiffness were used to build the spring-mass model for bolted repair. The predicted bolt loads agreed well with those obtained by FEM. The above two methods are simple and the bolt load can be easily obtained. However, FEM or analytical method is needed if the stress distributions around the holes are to be determined.

The majority of numerical investigations utilize two-dimensional finite element models. Three dimensional finite element models mostly concern lap joints of a few bolts with symmetric arrangements. Although versatile, the 3D finite element method is not suitable for bolted repair with multiple bolts because of the computational difficulties arising from iterative contact analysis and large degree of freedom. Actis and Szabo^[3], reported a paper about bonded and fastened repairs described in parametric form and used p-version of FEM. Shi et al^[4] utilized two-dimensional finite elements for the plate and the patch in conjunction with gap elements. The fasteners were modeled as assembly of a circular beam with its ends rigidly connected to two flexible discs. The discs were modeled with two-dimensional plane stress elements. Gap elements permitted modeling of the unknown contact regions between the discs and the hole boundaries in the plate and the patch.

As an alternative to the finite element method, Xiong and Poon^[8] introduced an analytical approach utilizing a variational formulation in conjunction with the complex potential theory to single- and double-lap joints with many bolts. Kradinov^[9] et al. introduced a semi-analytical method to determine the bolt load distribution in bolted single- and double-lap composite joints utilizing a complex potential-variational solution. The complex potential-variational method is computationally less demanding than the finite element method.

As the stress distribution is known, the strength of the bolted repair is evaluated with appropriate failure criterion by progressive damage method, characteristic length method^[11] or failure envelope method^[12], etc. Progressive damage method always results in long computing time that are not acceptable for preliminary sizing and for the optimization of aircraft structural. The most widely used design method for composite laminates with stress concentrations that is suitable for preliminary sizing and optimization is characteristic length method. However, the method has one problem: the “characteristic distance” is not a material property, it depends on both the material/layout and the geometry.

For bolted repair, the failure modes mainly include bolt hole failure and damage hole failure. The bolt hole under tensile load generally fails in three basic modes referred to as net-tension, shear-out and bearing modes. Among these three failure modes, as the bypass load is always much larger than the bolt bearing load, many of the bolted repair failed in net-tension failure modes^[5].

One of the most efficient methods for predicting net-tension failure strength is the Finite Fracture Mechanics model. The model was proposed by Leguillon^[13]. It assumes that the ultimate failure occurs by the propagation of kinematically admissible cracks with finite sizes. Finite Fracture Mechanics model have been successfully applied to the tensile strength prediction of open-hole laminates^[14] and the net-tension failure prediction of single-bolt composite joints^[15] by Camanho et al.

In the present work, the Finite Fracture Mechanics model was employed to predict the net-tension failure strength of bolted repairs. The stress distribution and the stress intensity factors were obtained using a two-stage analysis method together with parametrical p-version finite element method. The accuracy of the proposed method was validated through comparison with tensile test results conducted on three repaired laminates with different cutouts.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

As the damage occurs, the strength of the composite laminate is decreased. In order to reinforce the strength of the laminate, external patches are attached to the damaged area. The load across the damaged area is reduced by transmitting parts of the load through the patches. The method to predict the failure strength of the bolted repair is investigated in this paper. To simplify the study, the damaged area is simulated as a penetrated hole.

Consider a composite laminate with a damaged hole of radius, R , one external patch is bolted on the top to repair the damaged laminate. A tensile load is applied to the laminate as shown in Fig. 1. The patch can be either composite or metallic, are mechanically fastened to the composite skin with

multiple fasteners. The bolts and the corresponding holes are numbered from the left-bottom corner of the patch and noted as $1, 2, \dots, n$, respectively. The damaged hole is noted as 0. Without loss of generality, the model developed for this repaired structure with circular cutout in the following part can also be applicable to those laminates with elliptical cutout and oblong cutout. To avoid bending effect, the layup of the lamina and load are symmetric with respect to the middle plane. Therefore, the analysis may be simplified to a two-dimensional model. Finite Fracture Mechanics will be used to predict the tensile strength of this bolted repaired structure when net-tension failure occurs.

In this study, the analysis of the bolted repair on composite laminate is based on the following assumptions:

- 1) The bolts and holes are neat-fit.
- 2) The loads applied to bolt holes by the bolts follow a normal cosine distribution.
- 3) The arrangement of bolts is symmetric with respect to the centerline.
- 4) The effect of the friction on the bolts and clamping pressure is ignored.
- 5) Effect of bearing damage and matrix crack on load redistribution is ignored.
- 6) The ultimate failure plane is in the direction transverse to the loading.

Fig. 1 Typical bolted repair configuration

3. PREDICTION OF FAILURE

3.1 Failure criterion

For the sake of simplicity, a local coordinate system (x_i, y_i) is first defined for i -th hole. In this system, the x_i - and y_i - axes are parallel and transverse to the loading direction. Then, a new dimensionless local coordinate system (x_i, ξ_i) is defined with the origin at the edge of the hole where ξ_i is defined as

$$\xi_i = \frac{1}{\ell_i} \left(y_i - \frac{d_i}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where ℓ_i is the transformed variable and for a hole of diameter d_i , the value of the transformed variable, ℓ_i , can be chosen in the range of $0.5d_i \sim d_i$.

Fig. 2 Local coordinate system for i -th bolt

In this new coordinate system, the coupled stress-energy criterion reads^[15]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \sigma_x(\xi) d\xi = X_T^L \\ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \mathcal{K}_I^2(\xi) d\xi = \mathcal{K}_{IC}^2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where l is the crack extension just before its unstable propagation, σ_x is the tensile stress along y -axes in the vicinity of the hole boundary, X_T^L is the tensile strength of the unnotched laminate, \mathcal{K}_I is the mode I stress intensity factor and \mathcal{K}_{IC} is the critical mode I stress intensity factor.

It is possible to compute numerically, using the finite element method, the stress distribution and stress intensity factor when a unitary remote stress is applied and the data are fitted using polynomial functions as:

$$\sigma_x(\xi)\Big|_{\sigma_x^\infty=1} = \phi(\xi)\sigma_x^\infty\Big|_{\sigma_x^\infty=1} = \phi(\xi) = \sum_{i=0}^M \Phi_i \xi^{i-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{K}_I(\xi)\Big|_{\sigma_x^\infty=1} = \sigma_x^\infty\Big|_{\sigma_x^\infty=1} \psi(\xi) = \psi(\xi) = \sum_{i=1}^N \Psi_i \xi^{i-1} \quad (4)$$

where Φ_i and Ψ_j are the elements of the vectors Φ and Ψ , respectively. M and N are the orders of the polynomial functions.

The polynomial fitting functions ϕ and ψ are calculated using the commercial software StressCheck 9.2. A parametric finite element model is created using VB.NET together with StressCheck 9.2. Finally, the parameters that best fit the data are obtained via a least-squares curve fitting method. Our calculation shows that $\phi(\xi)$ and $\psi(\xi)$ can be approximated with high accuracy using a polynomial fitting function.

The stress and stress intensity factor can be calculated using the principle of superposition. As the non-linear effect such as bolt-hole clearance, friction and bearing damage are ignored, the stress in the vicinity of the hole boundary is proportional to the applied load. For an arbitrary remote stress, the stress distribution and stress intensity factor read:

$$\sigma_x(\xi) = \sigma^\infty \phi(\xi) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{K}_I(\xi) = \sigma^\infty \psi(\xi) \quad (6)$$

Inserting Eqs.(5) and (6) into Eq.(2), yields

$$\frac{\int_0^l \phi d\xi}{X_T^L} = \left(\frac{l \int_0^l \psi^2 d\xi}{\mathcal{K}_{IC}^2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Eq.(7) can be solved for $l(0 < l < 1)$. Substituting the value of l in one of (2) enables the calculation of the remote stress at failure, σ_f^∞ .

It should be noted that, for bolted repaired structure, it usually contains one damage hole and multiple bolt holes. The strength prediction of this type of structure can be done in two ways:

1) If the sizes of all the bolts are not the same, it is needed to predict the failure strength of each bolt hole using Eq.(7) and Eq.(2). The failure strength of each hole, including the damaged hole, is denoted as $\sigma_{fi}^\infty (i=0,1,\dots,n)$. Then the net-tension failure strength of the bolted-repaired structure is the minimum of these values, $\min(\sigma_{fi}^\infty)$.

2) If the sizes of all the bolts are the same, the critical bolt hole can be identified through detailed stress analysis. Then the failure strength of the critical bolt hole can be predicted, denoting as $\sigma_{fj}^\infty (n \geq j \geq 1)$. In addition, as the size of the damage hole is normally larger than that of the bolt hole, the failure strength of the damage hole should also be predicted, denoting as σ_{f0}^∞ . The net-tension failure strength of the bolted-repaired structure is the minimum of these two values, $\min(\sigma_{f0}^\infty, \sigma_{fj}^\infty)$.

In general, for the convenience of manufacturing, the sizes of all the bolts are often the same, so the second way can be used to predict the failure strength. As there is no need to predict the failure strength of all the bolt holes, the computation cost will be greatly reduced.

3.2 Computation of stress and stress intensify factor distributions

The knowledge of both the longitudinal stress distribution along the net-tension plane and the stress intensity factor for the case of two cracks emanating from a hole for the bolted-repaired structure is required. Due to the existence of many bolts in the bolted-repaired structure, if the global model is built and the stress around the holes and the stress intensity factors are accurately calculated, the mesh toward the hole boundary should be very refined, which will result in a large-scale model. In addition, for each crack length, a single model needs to be built and solved using non-linear solver, so it will be very time consuming. Therefore, this analysis method is not only difficult, but also may lead to too long calculation time and fail to predict the reasonable results. The two-stage analysis method

can adjust the model size according to the requirements of the calculation precision, and has the advantages of optimizing the calculation cost and improving the calculation precision. In bolted-repaired joints, the bolt load distribution and the load transferred ratio on the patch are less dependent on the mesh. Therefore, the first-stage model or global model with coarse mesh is used. As the stress distribution and the stress intensity factor severely depend on the mesh, the second-stage model with finer mesh is used. The main analysis steps are as follows:

- 1) Build the first-stage model under a remote stress $\sigma_x^\infty = 1$ and calculate the bearing load for each bolt. The bolt load was noted as $f_{oi} (\alpha = x, y, i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$.
- 2) Build the second-stage model as showed in Fig. 3 and the normal cosine distribution is employed as the traction boundary condition on the hole edge. Calculate the stress distribution around each hole. View the composite laminate as plate with multiple hole and apply the bolt load to the boundaries of the bolt hole. The stress around the hole can be extracted and fitted as $\sigma_{xi} (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$.
- 3) Identify the critical hole. The crack is arranged perpendicular to the loading direction in the maximum stressed point. View the composite laminate as plate with multiple hole and build the model of the plate with cracks. Extract the stress intensity factor and fitted as $K_{fi} (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$
- 4) Predict the failure strength using Eq.(7).
- 5) Compare the failure strength of each hole. The far filed stress corresponding to the earliest tensile failure is defined as the tensile strength of the repaired structure. The strength of the repair structure can be obtained as $\min(\sigma_{fi}^\infty)$.

Fig. 3 Second-stage model

4. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Three different damaged composite laminates after bolted repair were tested to validate the developed method. The cutouts of the three damaged laminates were circular hole, oblong hole and elliptical hole, respectively. The widths of cutouts were the same. In addition, the unrepaired laminate with circular cutout was also tested. Its strength was used to evaluate the repair efficiency of the repaired laminates. Configurations and dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig.4. Each group contained three specimens.

The composite laminate was manufactured by T300/QY8911 carbon/bismaleimide composite material with near-quasi-isotropic stacking sequence $[45/-45/0/-45/0/45/0/45/-45/0/-45/45/90/45/0/-45/90 / \bar{0}]_s$. Th symbol $\bar{0}$ refers to that the lay-up is odd symmetry about this ply. The lamina thickness was 0.12 mm. In general, to prevent galvanic corrosion, the composite structure should be connected with titanium alloy or stainless steel. Among these materials, titanium alloy has a higher specific strength and lower potential difference, is the ideal material. Therefore, the patch was manufactured by Titanium of TA15M, with a thickness of 2.5 mm. The bolts were MBF2313-07-250. The nominal diameter of the bolt was 5.76 mm.

An SUNS testing machine WAW-2000 with the load range of 2000 kN was used to test the static strength of bolted repaired structures. The test setup is shown in Fig. 5. The unidirectional tensile load was applied on the specimen at a rate of 2.5 mm/min until the collapse failure arrived.

From Table 1, it can also be seen that for repaired specimens with circular holes, two different failure modes were observed. One was found at the net-section of the damaged hole, and the other is at the net-section of the outermost row bolt hole. However, the failure strengths of the three specimens are almost the same. These results indicate that the failure strength corresponding to these two failure modes are almost the same.

Fig. 6 Typical failure modes: (a) damaged laminate; (b) repaired laminate with circular cutout; (c) repaired laminate with oblong cutout; (d) repaired laminate with elliptical cutout

Table 1 Tensile strength and failure modes of bolted repaired laminates

Specimens	Failure location	Tensile strength/MPa	C.V.%
Repaired laminate with oblong cutout	Damaged hole	242	6.8
Repaired laminate with circular cutout	Damaged hole & bolt hole	295	1.4
Repaired laminate with elliptical cutout	Damaged hole	258	7.8
Damaged laminate	Damaged hole	206	1.0

5. MODEL VALIDATION

As net-tension failure modes are found in the repaired structures, which are consistent with the assumptions of the developed method, the Finite Fracture Mechanics model is applicable to this problem. To apply the Finite Fracture Mechanics model, it is needed to obtain the stress distribution around the hole and the stress intensity factor in the vicinity of the hole boundary. p-version finite element method is used to model the bolted repair structure. As there are numerous bolts which distribute dispersively in the repaired structure, it will take much time and even almost impossible for traditional manual operating. Therefore, an auto and parametric modeling technique is needed to achieve this. In this paper, a generic, effective approach for auto modeling the repaired structure together with VB.NET is produced. The user can create the repaired structure geometry through a menu-driven interface and then generate a customized mesh according to the user's needs. Boundary conditions, bolt pattern, bolt diameter, bolt head type, applied load and material properties can also be set. The model was solved automatically. Based on the analysis results, the stresses around the hole and the stress intensity factors in the vicinity of the hole can be obtained. Furthermore, the bolt load ratios, characteristic length and failure strength can also be determined.

First, the bolt load distribution was calculated by using the first-stage model. Take the repaired structure with circular hole as an example, the finite element model is shown in Fig. 7. The finite element mesh consists of isoparametrically mapped 6-node triangular elements. The properties of the skin are assigned by using the equivalent material properties calculated by using the classical lamination theory. The fasteners are modeled as special fastener-type elements. They could only take compressive load at any point along their boundaries. Link elements are used to connect two fastener elements to simulate the bolt shear and bending effect. The Link element's stiffness is computed

according to Tate and Rosenfeld method. For the present countersunk titanium bolt with a diameter of 5.76 mm, its value is $K_s = 2.572 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}$. A uniform tensile load is applied to the right edge of the laminate. The left edge is fixed. Because the bolt load is less dependent on the mesh density, a coarse mesh is used in the first-stage model to improve the computational efficiency. The bolt load (F_x, F_y) are determined from analyzing the first-stage model.

Fig. 8 shows the bolt load distribution of the three repaired laminates. As the bolt load in the y -direction is much less than that in the x -direction, only the latter is presented in Fig. 8. The highest forces are exerted on the outermost bolts. As the bolts are placed nearer the vertical symmetry line of the patch, the amount of load they transfer will decrease, since the displacements near the symmetry line becomes smaller, and eventually vanish along the symmetry line. Also, the bolts transfer more load as they are placed near the cutout. This is mainly due to the skin stiffness decreased near the cutout area. Thus, more load is transferred to the patch.

Fig. 7 p-version finite element model of repaired structure with circular hole

Fig. 8 Load distribution of the bolted repair: (a) repaired laminate with circular cutout; (b) repaired laminate with oblong cutout; (c) repaired laminate with elliptical cutout

The local model is a porous plate structure with some bolt holes and a damaged hole. In order to obtain more accurate local analysis results, local models tend to adopt a finer mesh. As shown in Fig. 9, the p-version finite element analysis model for the stress distribution of the repaired structure with circular hole is presented. The bolt load of each bolt calculated in the global analysis is applied to the bolt hole in the local model. The far field load is sustained. The stress distributions around the holes of the repaired structure with circular cutout are shown in Fig. 10. In the same way, the stress

distributions can be obtained for the other repaired structures. It can be seen that the region with large stress mainly occurs in the bolt hole boundary.

Fig. 9 p-version finite element model for the calculation of stress distribution

Fig. 10 The stress distribution around the bolted hole and damaged hole

In order to obtain the fitting functions of the stress distribution data around the hole, it is necessary to determine the location of the maximum stressed point. For bolt holes, the maximum stressed point is in the $\pm 90^\circ$ direction of the holes. For damaged hole, the maximum stressed point is in the section where the width is the largest. The stresses are extracted over a distance from the maximum stressed point. In this paper, the transformed variable, $\ell_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, n)$ is chosen to be 4 mm. As the repaired structure with circular cutout and oblong cutout is symmetric, only one quarter of the bolt holes are analyzed. However, the outmost two rows of bolt holes are analyzed for the repaired structure with elliptical hole.

For repaired structure with circular cutout, Fig. 11(a) and (b) show the stress distribution around the bolt holes and damaged hole. Meanwhile, Fig. 11 (b) also gives the polynomial fitting curve of the damaged hole. It can be seen that the fitting curve and the calculated value are almost coincident. The results indicate that the polynomial function can be used to fit the stress distribution well.

Comparing the stress distribution of different bolt holes as shown in Fig. 11 (a), it can be seen that the stresses around the hole boundaries of bolt 1 is the highest. This bolt hole locates at the corner of the patch. As the stress around this hole boundary is the highest, it is identified to be the critical hole. Potential failure may occur at this position.

It should be noted that, the critical hole is different from that exerting the most load. As a result, for repaired structure, the critical hole can't be identified to be the most loaded hole. Detailed stress analysis is needed. Comparing the stress distribution of damaged hole and bolt hole, it can be seen that, the peak stress of the damaged hole is lower than that of the bolt hole. However, the gradient of the stress distribution is larger.

In the composite structure, the most stressed point is often the location where damage initiates, so the crack assumed in these positions. Fig. 12 shows the p-version finite element model for calculating the stress intensity factor of the bolt hole and damaged hole. The load and boundary conditions are the same as those in the stress analysis model. The stress intensity factors are shown in Fig. 13. For the sake of simplicity, only the stress intensity factor of the critical bolt hole and damaged hole are given.

Fig. 11 The stress distributions for the repaired structure with circular cutouts: (a) bolt hole, (c) damaged hole

Fig. 12 p-version finite element model for the calculation of stress intensity factor

Fig. 13 The stress intensity factors for the repaired structure with circular cutout, (a) the critical bolt hole, (b) the damaged hole

The unnotched strength for this lay-up is predicted using Tsai-Hill failure criteria together with first ply failure theory as

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_r^2} - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{X_r^2} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y_r^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} = 1 \quad (8)$$

where σ_1 is the stress along the fiber direction, σ_2 is the stress transverse the fiber direction and τ_{12} is the shear stress. The tensile strength of the unnotched laminate is $X_r^L = 667.5\text{MPa}$. To estimate the value of K_{IC} , the result of the test performed in the specimen with an 80 mm hole is used. Knowing the unnotched strength of the material and the notched strength of this stacking sequence, it is possible

to solve Eq.(2) for l and K_{IC} , which results in $K_{IC} = 20.81\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. Considering the variation of the tensile strength of the open-hole specimen, the value of K_{IC} is estimated when the tensile strength changes within $\pm 5\%$ around the mean value. If the tensile strength of the present large open-hole specimen is used, the calibrated critical stress intensity factor varies between $1.42\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ and $37.63\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. A small difference in tensile test results can lead to a huge change in the stress intensity factor.

Taking into account that for repaired structure with circular hole, as shown in Table 1, despite two failure modes are observed, but the failure strengths corresponding to the two failure modes are almost the same. Therefore, the critical stress intensity factor can be further corrected based on this result. The relationship between the failure strength of the repaired structure and the stress intensity factor was studied and the results are shown in Fig. 15. Take the critical stress intensity factor as the value when the failure strength corresponding to the two failure modes are equal. According to Fig. 15, this value is determined to be $K_{IC} = 40\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. This value is used to predict the failure strength of the three repaired structures and one unrepaired structure (the open-hole specimen). The predicted results are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the predicted results of the three repaired structures are close to the experimental values and the error is within 5%. The predicted failure modes are consistent with the experimental observations, which shows that the proposed model has high accuracy.

Fig. 14 The effect of the open-hole strength on the calibrated critical intensity factor

Fig. 15 The failure strength predicted using different critical intensity factors

Table 2 The failure load and failure mode obtained by using the Finite Fracture Mechanics model

Specimens	Failure strength/MPa			Failure mode	
	Experiment	Prediction	Error/%	Experiment	Prediction
Repaired laminate with oblong cutout	295	301	+2.0	Damaged hole & Fastener hole	Damaged hole & Fastener hole
Repaired laminate with circular cutout	258	262	+1.6	Damaged hole	Damaged hole
Repaired laminate with elliptical cutout	242	240	-0.8	Damaged hole	Damaged hole
Unrepaired laminate with circular cutout	206	215	+4.4	Damaged hole	Damaged hole

6. CONCLUSIONS

A finite fracture mechanics model was proposed to predict the net-tension strength of the bolted repair of composite laminates. Failure is predicted when both stress-based and energy-based are satisfied. The global-local method together with the p-version finite element method was used to compute the stress distribution and stress intensity factor around the holes. Bearing load acted on the hole by the bolt was simulated by cosine load distribution. The model is applicable for quasi-isotropic or near-quasi-isotropic laminates. It requires the longitudinal strength and the fracture toughness of the

laminates. Three different damaged laminates were tested to validate the model. The predictions are in good agreement with experimental results with a maximum error of 3.2%. The proposed model is quite suitable for the evaluation of the bolted repair design and for the generation of design charts.

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